

1 **Efficiency, quality, and management practices in health facilities providing outpatient**
2 **HIV services in Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia**

3

4 **Abstract**

5 Few studies have assessed the efficiency and quality of HIV services in low-resource settings
6 or considered the factors that determine both performance dimensions. To provide insights on
7 the performance of outpatient HIV prevention units, we used benchmarking methods to
8 identify best-practices in terms of technical efficiency and process quality and uncover
9 management practices with the potential to improve efficiency and quality. We used data
10 collected in 338 facilities in Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia. Data
11 envelopment analysis (DEA) was used to estimate technical efficiency. Process quality was
12 estimated using data from medical vignettes. We mapped the relationship between efficiency
13 and quality scores and studied the managerial determinants of best performance in terms of
14 both efficiency and quality. We also explored the relationship between management factors
15 and efficiency and quality independently. We found levels of both technical efficiency and
16 process quality to be low, though there was substantial variation across countries. One third
17 of facilities were mapped in the best-performing group with above-median efficiency and
18 above-median quality. Several management practices were associated with best performance
19 in terms of both efficiency and quality. When considering efficiency and quality
20 independently, the patterns of associations between management practices and the two
21 performance dimensions were not necessarily the same. One management characteristic was
22 associated with best performance in terms of efficiency and quality and also positively
23 associated with efficiency and quality independently: number of supervision visits to HIV
24 units.

25 **Keywords**

26 data envelopment analysis; HIV testing and counseling; prevention of mother-to-child
27 transmission; process quality; technical efficiency; sub-Saharan Africa

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43 **Highlights**

- 44 • In our sample of 338 health facilities providing outpatient HIV services in Kenya,
45 Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia, overall technical efficiency was low with a
46 mean score of 46%. Though there was substantial variation by country, all countries
47 could make sizeable efficiency gains.

- 48 • With a mean process quality score of 34%, overall process quality was low and quality
49 scores were low across the five countries. All countries could make considerable quality
50 improvements.

- 51 • One third of health facilities were classified in the best-performing group with above-
52 median efficiency and quality. Best-performing facilities were more likely to be larger
53 and privately owned than poor-performing facilities.

- 54 • Best-performing facilities were more likely to have more HIV unit supervisions and more
55 managerial meetings. They were also more likely to have reward schemes for good
56 performance. Conversely, they were less likely to use the rotation of well-performing
57 health staff as an incentive.

- 58 • Implementers should know that the patterns of associations between management
59 practices and technical efficiency and process quality are not necessarily the same for the
60 two dimensions of performance when they are considered independently. Number of
61 supervision visits to HIV units was positively associated with both efficiency and quality.
62 Of particular concern to implementers seeking to improve service quality, funding based
63 on the number of clients served was negatively associated with quality while funding
64 linked to inputs management was positively correlated.

65 **Background**

66 Despite significant progress achieved in addressing HIV globally, the annual number of new
67 HIV infections among individuals 15 years and older remains high and almost one third of
68 people living with HIV eligible for antiretroviral therapy (ART) do not receive treatment [1].
69 At the same time, following more than a decade of increases in financing for HIV services,
70 there has been a leveling off in recent years [2]. To increase access to HIV prevention and
71 treatment services in the context of constrained financial resources, there is an international
72 commitment to improve the allocation of HIV spending in low-resource settings by focusing
73 on the appropriate evidence-based interventions, populations, and geographic areas [3-11].
74 Likewise, improving technical efficiency in HIV service delivery, or ensuring that facilities
75 delivering HIV services use inputs to produce the largest quantity of outputs possible, is also
76 a global priority [12,13]. While this emphasis on improving the technical efficiency of HIV
77 services is necessary, the quality of these services also requires attention [14]. There are
78 concerns that there could be a trade-off between efficiency and quality in HIV service
79 delivery, and that quality could suffer if programs focus exclusively or excessively on cost
80 reduction without also paying attention to service quality [15].

81 The relationship between cost and quality of health services is complex and remains poorly
82 understood. Research on the relationship between health service costs and quality suggests
83 that costs and quality are jointly determined, but the direction of the association remains
84 uncertain [16]. While some research has focused on exploring the potential endogeneity in
85 this relationship [17], other studies, specifically on benchmarking, have treated efficiency and
86 quality as two independent dimensions of performance that one can benchmark on
87 simultaneously [18]. In the area of HIV service production, there is a growing literature on
88 the efficiency of health facilities delivering HIV services in low-resource settings [19-23].

89 However, there is only limited information available on the relationship between efficiency
90 and quality of HIV services in these settings [21,22], with only one study differentiating
91 between facilities that performed well in efficiency and quality from those that performed
92 poorly in both and those that exhibited a potential trade-off [22].

93 As implementers around the world work to improve HIV service delivery, it is critical that
94 they understand the relationship between efficiency and quality and the factors that determine
95 both dimensions. Facility-level management characteristics may explain some of the
96 variation in efficiency across facilities [21]. There are an increasing number of studies on the
97 relationship between facility-level management practices and productivity, which come
98 mostly from higher resource settings [24,25]. This work also finds that better management
99 techniques in health facilities are associated with improved quality of care [25-29], though
100 there is increasing evidence that managerial capacity in the healthcare sector is scarce,
101 especially in primary care environments [30]. In HIV service delivery, there is limited
102 evidence on the management factors that complement the production of efficiency and
103 quality or those that could generate a trade-off between them [23]. Implementers are more
104 likely to achieve global HIV service delivery goals if they understand how to avoid situations
105 where efficiency in the production of HIV prevention services is achieved at the expense of
106 the production of quality or vice versa.

107 To provide insights on the performance of outpatient HIV prevention units, we used
108 benchmarking methods to identify best-practices in terms of efficiency and quality and
109 uncover relevant factors with the potential to improve efficiency and quality. We focused on
110 technical efficiency, defined as the best combination of inputs to achieve an optimal level of
111 production [31-33] and process quality which refers to the way health services are provided
112 to deliver desired outcomes [34]. To evaluate efficiency, we used data envelopment analysis

113 (DEA) which produces a ranking of comparable decision-making units (DMUs) in terms of
114 their technical efficiency, in a context in which their production function must accommodate
115 multiple inputs and outputs [35]. DEA has been used extensively to assess the efficiency of
116 public services, including healthcare, but most DEA studies have considered efficiency only,
117 without considering service quality [36]. Among those DEA studies that have incorporated
118 quality, some have included quality as an exogenous variable in the second stage of the DEA
119 analysis [37], some have added quality as an output measure in the DEA model [38-43], and
120 others have treated efficiency and quality as independent dimensions that are benchmarked at
121 the same time [22,36,18]. In this study, we used the latter method of treating quality as an
122 independent dimension of performance. This approach allowed us to identify and
123 characterize best-performing facilities with high efficiency and high quality. We could also
124 identify organizational correlates of performance, drawing from a rich dataset on facility
125 characteristics including management practices. We hypothesized that there are management
126 practices associated with best practice (high efficiency and high quality) and that the patterns
127 of associations between management factors and efficiency and management factors and
128 quality may not be the same.

129 **Methods**

130 Fig. 1 shows an overview of our methods. We used data from a sample of health facilities
131 providing HIV prevention services collected as part of the “Optimizing the Response in
132 Prevention: HIV Efficiency in Africa” (ORPHEA) and the “Optimizing the Response in
133 Prevention and Treatment: HIV Efficiency in Nigeria” (ORPTHEA) studies. We conducted
134 our analysis in four steps. First, we estimated a technical efficiency score for each health
135 facility using DEA, coupled with a post-hoc analysis which factored in contextual
136 determinants of efficiency. Second, we estimated a process quality score using data from

137 medical vignettes using data-reduction techniques and reliability analysis. Third, we mapped
138 the relationship between the efficiency and quality scores and we studied the managerial
139 determinants of best performance in terms of both efficiency and quality using a positive
140 deviance approach. Fourth, we used seemingly unrelated regression to study the relationships
141 between management practices and efficiency and quality independently and to assess
142 whether some management factors might generate trade-offs between efficiency and quality.

143 **[insert Fig 1 about here - Fig 1. Overview of methods]**

144 *Data*

145 We used health facility data collected in analogous retrospective cross-sectional micro-
146 costing studies conducted in Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia [44-47].
147 Data covered 2011 for Kenya, South Africa, and Zambia, 2012 for Rwanda, and 2013 for
148 Nigeria. In-depth descriptions of the sampling and data collection methods used in Kenya,
149 Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia have been published elsewhere [46,47]. The sampling
150 strategy was standardized to collect information comparable across these four countries and
151 corresponding methods were used in Nigeria [44,45]. In each country, multistage sampling
152 was used to first select sub-national areas and then randomly select health facilities providing
153 at least one of the following outpatient services: HIV testing and counseling (HTC),
154 prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT), voluntary medical male circumcision
155 (VMMC), and in Nigeria also ART. Health facilities in selected sub-national areas were
156 enumerated along with information on the services of interest stratified by
157 ownership/management and level of service provision. Facilities were randomly sampled
158 within these strata using probability proportional to size, with preference given to sites
159 providing more than one outpatient service of interest. Facility sample size was calculated to
160 identify the minimal number of facilities necessary to detect statistically significant

161 associations between average unit cost per facility and the determinants of efficiency. The
162 analytic sample included 338 facilities with the sample breakdown by country as follows: 46
163 facilities in Kenya, 141 facilities in Nigeria, 52 facilities in Rwanda, 42 facilities in South
164 Africa, and 57 facilities in Zambia. Non-hospital health facilities (i.e., health posts, health
165 centers, and medical clinics) comprised two-thirds of the sample and hospitals made up the
166 remaining third. A standardized set of ORPHEA and ORPTHEM survey instruments were
167 developed. All instruments were piloted in all countries and minor adaptations were made for
168 each country setting. Data collection was staggered by country between October 2012 and
169 December 2013. Data on HIV prevention service inputs and outputs were collected
170 retrospectively by month for the entire previous calendar year, whereas data on the process
171 quality of services and the management characteristics of facilities correspond to the time of
172 data collection.

173 *Estimation of efficiency*

174 **DEA assumptions.** We estimated the efficiency of health facilities using DEA. DEA is a
175 nonparametric linear programming technique used to measure technical efficiency in a
176 sample of homogeneous decision-making units (DMUs) such as health facilities [48]. As a
177 data-driven method, DEA identifies a best practice frontier from the most efficient DMUs in
178 a sample and computes the distances between each DMU and the frontier, providing
179 efficiency scores in percentage terms (where 100% means full efficiency and 0% means full
180 inefficiency), and therefore an efficiency ranking of DMUs. DEA is one of two efficiency
181 analysis approaches along with Stochastic Frontier Analysis and it is the dominant approach
182 used to measure efficiency in health care [49,50].

183 We developed an output-oriented variable returns to scale (VRS) DEA model. Output-
184 oriented DEA models maximize outputs with a given amount of inputs [50]. This means that

185 our efficiency scores represent the proportional increases in outputs that DMUs could achieve
 186 using the same level of inputs, if they were on the efficient production frontier. We
 187 considered that the policy goal is to increase coverage and accessibility of HIV prevention
 188 services and not to minimize input use. We assumed a VRS production process, meaning
 189 that any change in output results in a variable change in input [48]. The returns to scale
 190 distribution of facilities by country is shown in Supplementary Material Table S1.

191 The output-oriented model is specified as follows:

$$\theta_n = \max \sum_{j=1}^q u_{jn} y_{jn} - w_n, \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\} \quad (1)$$

$$s. t. \sum_{i=1}^r v_{in} x_{in} \leq 1$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^q u_{jn} y_{jn} - w_n - \sum_{i=1}^r v_{in} x_{in} \geq 0, \forall n \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$$

$$u_{jn} \geq 0, v_{in} \geq 0 \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, r\}; \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, q\}.$$

$$w_n \in \mathbb{R}$$

192 Where θ_n is the technical efficiency score of the n -th DMU, u_{jn} and v_{in} are the relative
 193 weights of the i -th input and the j -th output of the n -th DMU (as defined below), and w_n
 194 indicates the different returns to scale. The values of outputs and inputs are positive or equal
 195 to zero, so u and v are positive vectors. The efficiency score that identifies the best practice
 196 frontier is found by solving this optimization problem. For all DEA analyses we used DEA
 197 Solver Pro (V13).

198 **Outputs and inputs.** Prior work on HIV efficiency informed the parametrization of our
199 multi-output VRS DEA model [19]. We defined outputs as the total number of clients-per-
200 year in the following categories: 1) number of HTC clients; 2) number of HTC clients
201 diagnosed as HIV-positive; 3) number of PMTCT clients tested; 4) number of PMTCT
202 clients diagnosed as HIV-positive; and 5) number of PMTCT clients receiving antiretroviral
203 prophylaxis. For the inputs, we considered labor (annual total cost of physicians, clinical
204 officers, nurses, counselors, social workers, laboratory staff, administrative staff), the
205 annualized capital cost of equipment and building, and utilities. We converted all cost data
206 from local currencies to United States dollars (US\$) using mid-year exchange rates for 2011
207 (Kenya: 88.81 Kenyan shillings and Zambia: 4860.7 Zambian kwacha) and 2012 (Rwanda:
208 614.3 Rwandan francs and South Africa: 8.21 South African rand), and then inflated to 2014
209 prices. All costs were adjusted for purchasing power parity (PPP) for non-tradable services,
210 primarily staff salaries. The descriptive statistics for the input and output variables used in the
211 DEA analysis are presented in Supplementary Material Table S2.

212 **Second stage of DEA model.** Since traditional DEA estimates suffer from finite sample bias,
213 Simar and Wilson propose a parametric bootstrap method to account for the (truncated) data-
214 generating process of efficiency, in which full efficiency ($\theta_i = 1$) is in principle possible but
215 occurs with zero probability [51]. Technically, this method combines truncated regression
216 analysis, simulation of the unknown error correlation, and calculation of bootstrapped
217 standard errors. Using this approach, we effectively parametrized different technologies for
218 each country and facility type *post-hoc*. The data generating process of efficiency is modeled
219 as:

$$220 \quad \hat{\theta}_i = E[\theta|z_i] = z_i\beta + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

221 where $\hat{\theta}_i$ is the bias-corrected efficiency score for facility i , z_i is a matrix of contextual
222 variables, and ε_i is an idiosyncratic error term.

223 **Contextual variables.** As contextual variables we included five variables that exogenously
224 determine differences in production technologies and other (unobserved) constraints that
225 affect the efficiency of outpatient HIV services: facility size (total number of outpatient
226 clients per year), supervisions by national-level Ministry of Health staff, type of facility
227 (hospital versus non-hospital), type of provider (public versus private), and country. The
228 inclusion of these variables was informed by previous work in which exogenously
229 determined contextual variables influenced different efficiency levels and thus determined
230 different production possibility frontiers [52]. Health facility size is a proxy for facility
231 catchment area, supervision visits by national-level staff represents independent national
232 oversight, type of facility indicates the difference between multi-product facilities and their
233 counterparts, type of provider signals the source of financing, while country reflects a series
234 of fixed characteristics that are part of the health system organization of each country. For the
235 second-stage DEA analysis, we used the Stata command *simarwilson*. Supplementary
236 Material Table S3 shows the results of the second-stage DEA analysis using a regression
237 model with bootstrapping in which the raw efficiency score is the dependent variable and the
238 contextual variables are on the left-hand side of the equation.

239 *Estimation of quality*

240 **Process quality.** This study used Donabedian's structure-process-outcome framework for
241 evaluating quality of care where structure signifies the characteristics of the facilities in
242 which care takes place, outcome refers to the impact of care on the individuals receiving care,
243 and process represents the activities undertaken by providers to deliver and by patients to
244 receive care [53]. The focus of our study was *process quality* measured by the technical

245 knowledge of health providers on the appropriate care strategies for patients who access HTC
246 and PMTCT services. Process quality captures the extent to which services provided include
247 the elements or processes involved in the production of services when adopting best practices
248 [54]. We developed a process quality score based on responses to vignette instruments used
249 to assess the extent to which providers reported following existing national HTC and PMTCT
250 guidelines [55,56].

251 Providers who had contact with HTC and PMTCT clients were randomly selected to
252 participate in vignette interviews. The medical vignettes presented respondents with
253 hypothetical scenarios describing typical HTC and PMTCT clients. Respondents were then
254 asked a series of questions on the processes they would follow with the clients in these
255 hypothetical scenarios. This method allowed us to assess the discrepancies between
256 recommended practice according to national guidelines and the procedures that providers
257 said they would follow, measuring provider competence. The HTC and PMTCT vignettes
258 have been described in more detail elsewhere [47].

259 **Quality score.** From the medical vignettes interviews, we constructed 107 indicators of
260 compliance with HTC and PMTCT guidelines. At the facility level, we computed the
261 percentage of providers at health facility *i* who reported complying with each of the
262 indicators of recommended practice. We used principal component analysis (PCA) to
263 construct the process quality score for each country separately [57]. We rotated the
264 covariance matrix in the varimax sense, retained the first principal component, and rescaled it
265 between 0 and 100. Reliability analysis was conducted, and the estimated Cronbach's α for
266 each country sample varied between 0.90 (Kenya) and 0.97 (Zambia). Supplementary
267 Material Fig. 1 provides additional information of the PCA analysis. We computed the
268 quality score using the Stata command *pca*.

269 We opted to use a data dimensionality reduction technique in the absence of a clear data
270 generating process (DGP) for quality, and because our goal was not to explain the correlation
271 among survey items (over a hundred). PCA analyzes all the variance of the set of variables
272 (survey items). We therefore adopted a simple approach given the high number of “factors”
273 in our data and our goal, which was to summarize the data into a single scalar that maximized
274 the variation in the quality score between clinics.

275 *Benchmarking the relationship between efficiency and quality*

276 To describe the relationship between health facility efficiency and quality, we first plotted the
277 second-stage DEA efficiency scores against the process quality scores, to reveal the
278 underlying heterogeneity of the two dimensions. We derived four efficiency-quality
279 quadrants using the medians of the efficiency and process quality scores to determine
280 thresholds [22]. The four quadrants reflect the possible configurations of efficiency and
281 process quality score combinations in our sample of health facilities: above-median
282 efficiency/above-median quality; above-median efficiency/below-median quality; below-
283 median efficiency/above-median quality; and below-median efficiency/below-median
284 quality.

285 Using a positive deviance approach to study the characteristics of the positive deviants or
286 best-performing facilities [58], we explored the organizational correlates—or management
287 practices—of the best-performing group, defined as those clinics at the intersection of those
288 facilities in the upper half of efficiency (θ) and those in the upper half of quality (Q):

$$y = \mathbb{1}(Pr(\theta \geq 0.5), Pr(Q \geq 0.5)) \quad (3)$$

289 We used a linear probability model with heteroskedasticity-consistent standard errors to
290 explore these associations. We sought to identify the management characteristics associated

291 with an increase in the probability of a health facility being classified in the quadrants
292 described above.

$$Pr(Y_i = y|X_i) = X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i \quad (4)$$

293 Where X_i includes binary and count variables that characterize the management practices
294 described below.

295 *Managerial determinants of efficiency-quality*

296 **Simultaneous equations estimation.** To explore the relationships between management
297 practices and efficiency and quality independently and assess whether some factors might
298 generate trade-offs between efficiency and quality, we estimated regression equations for
299 health facility efficiency and quality simultaneously using seemingly unrelated regression
300 (SUR) [59]. The SUR system of equations is based on the following assumptions: the
301 existence of correlation of error terms across regression equations, and/or a relationship
302 between the parameters included in the different equations of the equation system [59]. We
303 assumed that both observable and unobservable factors simultaneously influence efficiency
304 and quality with observed management practices concurrently influencing both health facility
305 efficiency and quality.

306 The estimating equations were specified as follows:

$$307 \quad \hat{\theta}_i = X_{1i}\beta_{1i} + \varepsilon_{1i} \quad (5)$$

$$308 \quad \hat{Q}_i = X_{2i}\beta_{2i} + \varepsilon_{2i} \quad (6)$$

309 where $\hat{\theta}_i$ is the bias-corrected efficiency score for facility i , and $\hat{Q}_i$ is the quality score. Since
310 the strength of the association between management practices and performance is unknown *a*
311 *priori*, we adopted an agnostic regression approach and implemented stepwise techniques for

312 model selection. Therefore, X_{1i} aggregates the selected management practices for the
313 efficiency equation, and X_{2i} for the quality equation. We set a threshold significance level of
314 0.2 and used only those covariates that showed a variance inflation factor (VIF) smaller than
315 2 to avoid inference problems due to multicollinearity. The β coefficients represent the
316 partial correlation between a given management practice and the associated outcome, and
317 $\varepsilon_{1i}, \varepsilon_{2i}$ are idiosyncratic error terms. We conducted the Breusch-Pagan test for the null
318 hypothesis that the covariance matrix of residuals is diagonal, i.e. $Cov(e_{1i}, e_{2i}) = 0$.

319 **Management practice variables.** We derived the management variables we examined from
320 responses to questions on facility-level management practices. These questions were based
321 on the World Management Survey (WMS) developed by Bloom and Van Reenen for
322 manufacturing firms [60] and subsequently applied to health facilities [24-29]. We adapted
323 the questions to capture relevant information for health facilities delivering HIV services in
324 low-resource settings. Managers responsible for HTC and PMTCT services were interviewed
325 in person on management practices in five domains: operations management, performance
326 monitoring, target setting, people management, and community engagement. We coded the
327 management variables so that higher values indicated more or better management. The
328 practices included in this analysis were: total number of supervisions made to HIV units in a
329 year; whether funding received by facilities was based on the number of clients served;
330 whether funding received by facilities was based on the quantity of inputs used; whether
331 facilities or employees received payments or rewards for good performance in providing HIV
332 services; whether well performing staff were rotated; whether staff received training as a
333 result of good performance; participation of local community on facility governing board;
334 existence of community advisory councils providing facility oversight; and frequency of
335 managerial meetings in a year during which management and administrative issues related to

336 HIV service delivery were discussed. Supplementary Material Tables S4 and S5 provide
337 additional details on the management practices used in the analysis.

338 **Results**

339 Fig. 2 shows the histogram of bias-corrected technical efficiency scores obtained from our
340 DEA analysis (Supplementary Material Table S6 presents both the raw efficiency scores and
341 the bias-corrected efficiency scores by country). These results show that average efficiency in
342 the sample was 46%. The results also indicate considerable variation in the efficiency scores
343 across the five countries. Facilities in South Africa had the highest average efficiency score
344 with a mean of 73%. Rwandan facilities had the second highest score with a mean of 67%.
345 Kenya, Nigeria and Zambia followed with average scores of 47%, 37% and 28%,
346 respectively.

347 **[insert Fig 2 about here - Fig 2. Distribution of bias-corrected technical efficiency scores**
348 **by country]**

349 The distribution of process quality scores by country are shown in Fig. 3. The average
350 process quality score in the sample was 34% with over 50% of health facilities having a
351 process quality score of 26% or less. The distribution of average process quality scores in the
352 sample was skewed, with only a few health facilities having high process quality scores.
353 Average process quality ranged from 22% in Nigeria to 51% in Kenya. Kenya had the largest
354 proportion of health facilities with process quality scores above 50%.

355 **[insert Fig 3 about here - Fig 3. Distribution of process quality scores by country]**

356 Fig. 4 maps the bias-corrected technical efficiency scores and the process quality score for
357 each health facility in the sample. The median values of the efficiency and process quality
358 scores determined the distribution of facilities across the four quadrants. South African

383 comparing the best-performing facilities (n=114) to the rest of the sample (n=224), we found
384 that 71% of the best-performing facilities were private, compared to 45% of facilities in the
385 rest of the sample. We also found that best-performing facilities were significantly larger in
386 terms of size of HTC unit (4,836 vs 3,028 clients per year) and total number of outpatient
387 clients (6,161 vs 3,603 clients per year).

388 Table 1 presents results from a linear probability regression model examining the
389 management practices associated with the likelihood of being in the best-performing group of
390 facilities (above-median efficiency/above-median quality). We report the marginal changes in
391 the probability of belonging to the above-median efficiency/above-median quality quadrant
392 compared to being in the other three quadrants (below-median efficiency/below-median
393 quality, below-median efficiency/above- median quality, and below-median quality/above-
394 median efficiency quadrants) given a discrete change in each variable and holding the rest of
395 the covariates at their mean values. Facilities with above-median levels of efficiency and
396 quality were 1.6 percentage points (p.p.) more likely to have an additional HIV unit
397 supervision. The best-performing facilities were 8 p.p. more likely to have an additional
398 managerial meeting. The best-performing facilities were less likely to use rotation of well-
399 performing health staff as an incentive (19.1 p.p.). Compared to poor-performing facilities,
400 facilities with above-median levels of efficiency and above-median levels of quality were
401 also more likely to receive rewards for good performance providing HIV services (14 p.p.)
402 and to receive training for good performance (11 p.p.). Supplementary Material Table S8
403 shows results for sensitivity analysis conducted around the cut-off points used to define the
404 best-performing group.

405 **[insert Table 1 about here - Table 1. Linear probability regression results examining the**
406 **management practices associated with the likelihood of being in the best-performing**
407 **group of facilities (above-median efficiency/above-median quality)]**

408 Table 2 shows results of simultaneous equations to identify the management factors
409 associated with efficiency and quality simultaneously. To test the existence of a potential
410 relationship between the two equations justifying the use of seemingly unrelated regression,
411 we tested the correlation between the residuals of the two equations. We found that although
412 the correlation was weak (0.0719), the Breusch-Pagan test for diagonality of the variance-
413 covariance matrix of the disturbances of the two equations was statistically insignificant (p-
414 value 0.2161). We therefore failed to reject the null hypothesis of zero correlation between
415 the two equations. The first results column shows the results for efficiency and the second
416 shows the results for process quality. The number of supervision visits to HIV units was
417 positively associated with both efficiency and quality. An additional supervision visit was
418 associated with a 1.5 p.p. increase in the bias-corrected technical efficiency score and with a
419 0.69 p.p. increase in the process quality score. Funding based on the number of clients served
420 was associated with a 8.2 p.p. decrease in the quality score. Funding linked to quantity of
421 inputs used in health facilities was positively associated with the quality score (7.1 p.p.).
422 Rewards for good performance in the provision of HIV services provided to the facility or
423 staff was positively associated with the efficiency score (16.7 p.p.). Similarly, we found a
424 positive association between the number of meetings and the efficiency score (3.5 p.p. per
425 additional meeting). The existence of a community advisory council was negatively
426 associated with the efficiency score (6.6 p.p.). In contrast, the participation of local
427 community in the facility governing board increased quality by 6.4 p.p. compared to facilities
428 with no local community representation on the governing board.

429 **[insert Table 2 about here - Table 2 Seemingly Unrelated Regressions (SUR) results**
430 **examining the relationship between management practices and efficiency and quality**
431 **simultaneously]**

432 **Discussion**

433 In this analysis of technical efficiency and process quality in 338 health facilities providing
434 outpatient HIV services in Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia, we found
435 overall levels of both efficiency and quality to be rather low, which is troubling. The mean
436 technical efficiency score in the sample was 46% and the mean process quality score was
437 34%. We found substantial variation in both technical efficiency and process quality across
438 countries. Whereas we found facilities in South Africa and Rwanda to be more efficient,
439 facilities in Nigeria and Zambia had relatively low levels of technical efficiency. Process
440 quality scores were highest in Kenya and lowest in Nigeria. Our findings on efficiency were
441 consistent with most other studies on the technical efficiency of HIV services in similar
442 settings [21-23], though one study of facilities providing HIV treatment in Zambia found
443 mean efficiency to be significantly higher [19]. While we are unaware of previous work
444 using vignettes to assess HIV service process quality, the low levels of quality we found were
445 comparable to those of studies that have used this technique to examine quality of other
446 health services in low-resource settings [61,56,62-66].

447 Mapping technical efficiency scores against process quality scores, we found that one third of
448 facilities were mapped in the best-performing group (above-median efficiency/above-median
449 quality). One fourth of facilities were mapped in the below-median efficiency/below-median
450 quality quadrant which is concerning. Just over 40% of facilities were mapped in the above-
451 median efficiency/below-median quality and below-median efficiency/above-median quality
452 quadrants. A recent study on the efficiency of health facilities integrating HIV and sexual

453 reproductive health services in Kenya and Swaziland applied a similar mapping approach but
454 used the 75th percentile instead of the median as the threshold to divide the four quadrants
455 [22]. They found that no facilities were mapped in the high efficiency and high quality
456 quadrant, two-thirds of facilities mapped in the low efficiency and low quality quadrant, and
457 one-third of the facilities were distributed in the other two quadrants.

458 Delving into the characteristics of positive deviant facilities with above-median technical
459 efficiency scores and above-median process quality scores, we found that most best-
460 performing facilities were Rwandan, South African, and Kenyan. We found that best-
461 performing facilities were more likely to be privately owned than poor-performing facilities.
462 Best-performing facilities were also significantly larger than poor-performing facilities in
463 terms of size of HTC unit and total number of outpatient clients. This finding on patient
464 volume and what appears to be associated provider specialization is consistent with study
465 findings from other settings and health areas that observed that patient volume and provider
466 specialization were associated with better quality in terms of process quality and health
467 outcomes [67-69].

468 Our assessment of the management characteristics of positive deviant facilities suggests that
469 facility-level management characteristics may explain some of the variation in the
470 performance of HIV prevention service delivery. Positive deviants or best-performing
471 facilities were more likely than poor-performing facilities to implement certain management
472 practices and less likely to implement others. Assessing the relationship between facility
473 management characteristics and best performance in terms of both technical efficiency and
474 process quality together, we found that compared to poor-performing facilities, best-
475 performing facilities were more likely to have more HIV unit supervisions and more
476 managerial meetings. Best-performing facilities were also more likely to have rewards for

477 good performance providing HIV services and to have training for good performance.
478 Conversely, best-performing facilities were less likely than poor-performing facilities to use
479 the rotation of well-performing health staff as an incentive.

480 Our findings also suggest that to improve HIV service delivery, understanding the
481 management practices of positive deviants is important but not sufficient. Considering the
482 relationship between management practices and technical efficiency and process quality
483 independently, we found that the patterns of associations were not necessarily the same for
484 the two dimensions of performance. One of the management characteristics was positively
485 associated with both the efficiency score and the quality score: number of supervision visits
486 to HIV units. Some management characteristics had significant associations with the
487 efficiency score, but not with the quality score or vice versa. Rewards for good performance
488 and number of meetings were positively associated with efficiency whereas the existence of a
489 community advisory council was negatively associated with the efficiency score. The
490 associations between these management characteristics and quality were not statistically
491 significant. Conversely, though the associations between these management factors and
492 efficiency were not statistically significant, funding based on the number of clients served
493 was negatively associated with process quality and funding linked to the quantity of inputs
494 used was positively associated with quality. We did not find any evidence of a possible trade-
495 off between efficiency and quality—we did not find management practices that were
496 positively associated with the technical efficiency score and negatively associated with the
497 process quality score or vice versa.

498 One of the strengths of this study is that we benchmarked at the same time both the technical
499 efficiency and process quality of facilities delivering HIV prevention services. Our study
500 contributes to the literature on the joint analysis of efficiency and quality conceiving these

501 two concepts as two separate dimensions [36]. Our study also expands on previous work
502 mapping facilities delivering HIV services [22] since it not only describes the relationship
503 between efficiency and quality but also describes the relationship between management
504 factors and efficiency and quality. Another strength of the study is our operationalization of
505 the management variables. Studies exploring the management practices of health facilities
506 often construct additive management scores [26-28,23,29] making it difficult to identify the
507 specific actions implementers can and should take to impact productivity. We studied
508 discrete management variables that providers can recognize and act on.

509 Several limitations should be kept in mind when considering our findings. ORPHEA and
510 ORPTHEM study data covered different years—2011 for Kenya, South Africa, and Zambia,
511 2012 for Rwanda, and 2013 for Nigeria. Because we retrospectively collected information on
512 inputs, prices, and outputs, data on process quality of services and management
513 characteristics of facilities correspond to slightly different time periods, although there was
514 never more than a 12-month difference. We used routine monitoring data to capture
515 information on outputs, and the level of detail, quality, and completeness of these data varied
516 across facilities. Our quality measure derived from medical vignettes assessing the technical
517 knowledge of health providers is focused on process quality, we did not have measures of
518 structural quality or patient outcomes. Our measures of contextual variables were limited, and
519 it is possible that we may have missed relevant factors related to the organization of the
520 health systems in each country. Contextual characteristics such as national governance,
521 financing mechanisms, budget allocations, donor relations and others may be important in
522 explaining variations in efficiency and quality [70,71]. Although our questionnaires on
523 management practices were based on previous studies, we may have omitted some practices
524 relevant to each of the health systems in the five countries. In terms of our analyses, because
525 the DEA approach orders health facilities according to the efficiency frontier generated from

526 the sample analyzed, results might be different if comparisons were to be performed within
527 countries given the change in the point of reference. This is likely to underpin the differences
528 between our results on the efficiency of Zambian facilities and results in the previous study
529 mentioned above, which found a mean efficiency score of 83% among Zambian facilities
530 providing HIV treatment [19]. Our study findings on the levels of efficiency and quality
531 should not be generalized to other settings. However, our findings provide useful insights on
532 the relationships between management factors and efficiency and quality.

533 **Conclusions**

534 We found important differences in the technical efficiency of health facilities providing
535 outpatient HIV services in Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, South Africa, and Zambia; all countries
536 could make substantial efficiency gains. Of particular concern, process quality scores were
537 low across the five countries; all countries could make considerable quality improvements.
538 Only one third of facilities were mapped in the best-performing group. We identified several
539 management practices associated with best-performance in terms of both efficiency and
540 quality. We also found that when considering efficiency and quality independently, the
541 patterns of associations between management practices and the two dimensions of
542 performance were not necessarily the same. We found one management characteristic
543 associated with best-performance in terms of efficiency and quality which was also positively
544 associated with efficiency and quality independently: number of supervision visits to HIV
545 units. As implementers around the world work to improve HIV service delivery, it is critical
546 that they understand the relationship between management characteristics and efficiency and
547 quality so that they can identify the practices that they can influence to improve performance.
548 Additional research exploring the quality and efficiency of HIV service delivery in low-

549 resource settings is urgently needed, as is further investigation of the causal relationship
550 between management practices and efficiency and quality.

551

552 **Abbreviations**

553 ART: antiretroviral therapy; DEA: data envelopment analysis; DMU: decision making unit;
554 HTC: HIV testing and counseling; ORPHEA: Optimizing the Response in Prevention: HIV
555 Efficiency in Africa; ORPTHEA: Optimizing the Response in Prevention and Treatment:
556 HIV Efficiency in Nigeria; PCA: principal components analysis; PMTCT: prevention of
557 mother-to-child transmission; SUR: seemingly unrelated regression; VRS: variable returns to
558 scale.

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